

(Re)Connecting Urban Natures

An interdisciplinary symposium on transforming human-nature relations in cities

The Global Symposium will be held at RMIT Europe, Media-TIC Building, Level 5, c/Roc Boronat 117, 08018, Barcelona. You can find it online here: <http://www.rmit.eu/en/about-rmit-europe>.

Final Agenda

Sunday 23 February – BCN Walking Tour

3pm - To meet under the Arc de Triumf. Ferne's Whatsapp: +34 645469414. This tour could include the possible purchase of transport ticket. Please wear your walking shoes!

7pm – To meet at a tapas bar in the city (self-funded).

Monday 24 February – Public launch & day 1 Global Symposium

Green Infrastructure and Nature Based Solutions Seminar

Hosted and supported by RMIT Europe

9:30am – arrival, registration and coffee

Public Launch Event: Green Infrastructure and Nature Based Solutions Seminar

10am – 10:10 - Welcome to the panel by Marta Fernandez, Director, RMIT Europe

10:10 – 11:15 – Overview presentations

10:20 - Susana Saiz, *Environmental and Sustainability Advisory, Associate Director, ARUP*

10:30 - Martí Franch, *Founder Manager, EMF Landscape Architects*

10:40 - Núria Noguer, *Urban planning Director, OUA Group*

10:50 - Margarida Pares, *Head of Biodiversity, Barcelona City Council*

11:00-11:45am – panel discussion

11:45-12noon – short break

12:00 – Snapshot of NBS case studies across Barcelona and the world

12:00-12:05 – Ferne Edwards to introduce

Presenters:

12:05 - Cristina Yacoub Lopez, *Leitat*

12:10 - Adela Martinez, *Huertos in the Sky*

12:15 - Carles Caballero, *Ajuntament de Terrasa, Anella Verda*

12:20 - Chiara Farinea, *IAAC & URBINAT*

12:25 – Anna Gras, *Espigoladors*

12:30 – Filka Sekulova, *Naturvation*

12:35 – 12:40 - Cristina Gonzalez, *EdiCitNet, Ajuntament de Sant Feliu de Llobregat*

12:40 – 1:30pm – Summary discussion led by Leah Gibbs and Ferne Edwards

1:30pm – lunch

The EdiCitNet project has received

2:30pm – Welcome to the (Re)Connecting Urban ‘Natures’ Symposium

Convenors: Dr Ferne Edwards^{1&2}, Dr Cecily Maller², Dr Brian Coffey²

¹RMIT Europe, ²RMIT Australia, Centre for Urban Research

Supported by

EdiCitNet, People, Nature, Place and Critical Urban Governance research programs

Introduction by Ferne Edwards

3pm-6pm – Session 1: Place and place-making

3:30pm - Jordi Honey-Rosés and Oscar Zapata - *Changes to mood, stress and wellbeing in a green street: A Field Experiment*

4:00pm - Leah Gibbs - *City and Sea*

4:30pm - Soledad Martínez - *Care and Companionship as Place-making: Lessons from Everyday Life Relationships with Urban Green*

5:00pm-6pm - Longer discussion at end of session

6:00pm –8pm - Cocktail reception for guests of the symposium

Tuesday 25 February - Day 2 (Re)Connecting Urban ‘Natures’

8:45am – Arrival time

9-1:30pm – Session 2: Care and caring

9am – Wendy Steele - *Caring-with the Wild City*

9:30am - Gordon Waite, Maddison Shaw and Natascha Klocker - *Troubling greenspace: wellbeing, urban natures, talanoa and first-generation Samoan migrants living in South West Sydney, Australia*

10:00am - Deborah Nadal - *Who cares and for whom? The issue of urban India with street dogs, rabies control, and the One Health*

10:30 – Short discussion for presenters for distance

11:00am – Coffee break

11:30am - Jeannine-Madeleine Fischer - *Good Plants gone Bad – Weeding in Auckland*

12:00 – Russell Hitchings - *Speaking of nature benefits: strategies of interaction and situational stigma*

12:30 – Cecily Maller – *How are we (already) getting along with ‘nature’ in cities: Microbiome and multispecies perspectives*

1:00pm - Discussion

1:30pm – lunch

The EdiCitNet project has received

2:30-5:00pm – Session 3: Governance and governing

2:00pm - Brian Coffey – *Who speaks for nature in the city?*

2:30pm - Ida Nilstad Pettersen - *Street trees within complexes of urban design and governance practice*

3pm - Brian Coffey - *Towards good governance of urban greening*

3:30pm – short break

4pm - Jolein Bergers - *Socio-spatial mappings of ecological practices in the Vogelenzangbeek*

4:30pm – Ferne Edwards – *Governing diverse natures in edible cities*

5pm – Longer discussion

5:30pm - Michelangelo Giampaoli - *Cemeteries: The forgotten urban nature*

6pm – close

6pm – 9pm – Drinks and dinner out in town

Wed 26 Feb. – (Re)Connecting Urban Natures / Start Writing Retreat

8:45am – Arrival time

9-1:30pm – Session 4, Imagining possible futures

9am - Donna Houston - *Urban Political Ecology at the Edges of Extinction*

9:30am - Anibal G. Arregui - *Pigs in beta: towards a protoecology of Barcelona*

10:00am - Mathilda Rosengren - *Urban trees as “furniture”?*

10:30am - Rita Campos - *What really matters? A photo-elicitation study about children’s perspectives of urban settings*

11:00am – Coffee break

11:30am – longer discussion and next steps

1:00pm - lunch

4pm - Tentative departure for writing retreat

Thursday 27 February – Writing Retreat

Friday 28 February - Writing Retreat

Saturday 29 February - Writing Retreat

Sunday 1 March – End Writing Retreat

The EdiCitNet project has received

